

IMPROVE GRAMMAR SKILL USING SOME TECHNIQUES FOR THE STUDENTS

Mamarajabova Sadoqat Dilmurod qizi

Student of Termez State University

The Faculty of Foreign Philology

Abstract: Grammar is one part to improve four skills that we also known. To enhance grammar skill, we have to prefer the accurately method as a way in studying grammar. Grammar is a rule to create a sentence, it can influence the way of communication can be delivered and received. It is supported by Argawati (2017) that in conclusion, grammar is a rule of language which has conventional arrangement to make sentence and convey larger meaning. Some of them are tenses, passive voice, sentence, parts of speech, conditional sentences, and many more. This article shows some techniques to develop grammar skill.

Keywords: grammar, native language, tenses, parts of speech.

English becomes international language to unite the world. In the era of globalization, learning English is very important because English able for linking and make easily people in the most of countries are communicated each other based on the development in the field of economic, business, education and also politic, Parmawati (2018). It applies to interact each other, peculiarly with the foreigners. In building a god communication we should understand the rules of the way to interact. To attain that goal, we necessary to dominate some prevalent skills as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. In addition, those master spelling, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar as the basis for accomplishing each skill. According to Kolln & Funk (2009) grammar is certainly a common word. Such as stated by Ingemann & Crystal (2008) grammar is seen as an inherently meaningful (or “symbolic”) component of the theory, linking semantic (viewed in conceptualist terms) and phonology.

Grammar is set of formal rules which projects a finite set of sentences upon the potentially infinite set of sentences that constitute the language as a whole, and it does this in an explicit manner, assigning to each a set of structural descriptions. Farisatma, Nasmilah, & Rahman (2017) stated grammar is one of the English language elements which is very important to be mastered in all skill of language such as speaking, reading, and writing. That opinion is also disclosed by

Haryudin & Argawati (2018) that stated grammar covers many themes that may confuse students on memorizing and understanding them.

This article will give you some tips for how to get better at grammar and improve your writing skills:

✓ **READ, READ, READ**

This tip might seem obvious, but it is the most important one. Read written English. You can read novels, textbooks, or newspapers – anything that makes you excited to keep reading and learning. Whether or not English is your native language, your brain will learn it better through repeated exposure. The more you read, the more you’ll naturally understand how proper grammar works. Even if you don’t know all the rules yet, reading will help you build an intuition for the written language.

✓ **CONSULT A GRAMMAR MANUAL**

A grammar manual can help you understand why English grammar works the way it does. Knowing the rules isn’t a replacement for having a natural intuition for grammar – you need to build both simultaneously – but it can certainly help you avoid written mistakes. If you don’t have a grammar manual yet, you can try the Grammar in Use series by Raymond Murphy or Garner’s Modern Usage by Bryan A. Garner. You can also use a common style guide like the Chicago Manual of Style or the Associated Press Style.

✓ **USE A GRAMMAR CHECKER**

A grammar checker can help you make your writing sound fluent and professional, even if you’re still learning the rules. ProWritingAid can help you improve your grammar skills with every new piece you write. Look at the issues

ProWritingAid catches in your work to see if you repeatedly make the same grammar mistakes. Read the explanations for what you're doing wrong and see the different ways you can correct the mistake. For example, if you're conjugating your verbs incorrectly, ProWritingAid will highlight every instance of that mistake and help you fix it.

✓ **LEARN THE PARTS OF SPEECH**

There are nine types of words in the English language: nouns, pronouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, prepositions, conjunctions, interjections, and articles. Study these nine parts of speech and how they link. You'll need to know which role each word plays in order to use it correctly in a sentence.

✓ **LEARN THE RULES OF SENTENCE STRUCTURE**

Sentence structure encompasses many topics, from, the difference between independent and dependent clauses, to the necessary elements the comprise a complete sentence. Language these rules will help you create more complex sentences in your writing.

✓ **PLAY GRAMMAR GAMES**

Most people learn better by playing games than by studying. You can find plenty of grammar games online which put your skills to the test in a fun and exciting way. You can try the Quiz Your English app, which allows you to compete against your friends. If you're at a more advanced level, you can try Proof It, a game where you look for grammar and punctuation mistakes in English sentences. If you're learning English as a second language, you can try Fluence, which takes real videos and turns them into games.

CONCLUSION

Prior to mastering four skills, the students' have to master the rules in using English language. The rules in language are called grammar. Grammar is the highest important thing in all skills because it has a role as a root to development our skills. For the students' Junior High School level, learning English grammar will be more difficult to learn. In particular learning tenses, due to it has varieties of them. Besides

the material, the way to deliver the lesson very extremely in influencing how the students can learn and understand the lesson.

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